

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Application of biofertilizer to improve rye yields, water and nutrient availability

Spain is one of the EU's most vulnerable countries to the effects of global warming and soil exploitation, which will result in higher temperatures and decreased nutrient and water availability, among other things. Crop yields are reduced as a result. Rye agriculture in the area is extensive in terms of machinery and pesticide use, with minimal fertilization and no rotation, except for fallow periods to prevent soil depletion. The main objective of this case study is to use novel strategies based on rotations and use formulations based on microorganisms to increase nutrient availability and water retention while reducing the frequency of crop-related disease in the soil and increasing grain production.

Four plots (22 x 500 m) were selected in "Finca La Junquera" located in Caravaca (Murcia, SE Spain). The first cycle of the rotation was the Rye crop, it was carried out from December 2020 to July 2021. Four treatments were applied: a) F100 (typical fertilization- based on pig slurry end organic-pellet); b) BA+FU (nutrient solubilizing biological bacteria and fungi+ 30% fertilization reduction); c) BA (nutrient solubilizing bacteria+ 30% fertilization reduction); d) F70 (fertilization reduction). Fertilization reduction in treatment plots had no effect on rye yield. There were no statistically significant differences in grain-specific weight between the four treatments.

1. Rye plantation in Mediterranean South region (Spain).

KEYWORDS

Biofertilizers, rye yield, water availability, nutrient availability, pig slurry, organic-pellet.

AUTHORSHIP

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